

Priming Snake-in-the-Box Search with Seed Snakes in $n-1$ and $n-2$ Dimensions

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Abstract. The Snake-in-the-Box problem seeks the longest possible induced path ("snake") in the edge graph of an n -dimensional hypercube. The best results known in hypercubes of dimension 10 or higher come from extending lower-dimensional seed snakes. This paper describes multiple methods for primed (seeded) search and presents potentially new record lengths of 1461 and 2892 for snakes in 12 and 13 dimensions, respectively.

1 Introduction

The n -dimensional hypercube graph Q_n is a regular graph with 2^n vertices and $n \cdot 2^{n-1}$ edges. The Snake-in-the-Box problem seeks to find the longest induced path in Q_n . No two non-consecutive vertices in a snake's path may be adjacent to each other on the hypercube, a constraint that is essential to the character and complexity of the problem.

Maximum possible snake length is known in dimensions 8 and below (the problem is completely solved in those dimensions). Research in higher dimensions places upper and lower bounds on snake length. This paper considers lower bounds only, which are demonstrated by example snakes in various dimensions.

Figure 1 shows a 3-dimensional hypercube (i.e., a cube) with unit-length edges and one vertex at the origin. Vertices are labeled with binary numbers 000 through 111 formed from Cartesian coordinates. The shaded path shows a length-4 snake with vertex sequence 000, 001, 011, 111, 110.

Fig. 1. A snake in 3 dimensions.

Numbering vertices in binary allows for concise expression of the constraints in the Snake-in-the-Box problem: labels of consecutive vertices in a snake's path differ in exactly one bit position (i.e., have Hamming distance 1) whereas labels of non-consecutive vertices differ in multiple places (Hamming distance > 1). The Snake-in-the-Box problem arose in the study of coding theory [4] and continues to have application in that field. Thomas Drapela's primer [3] reviews the history of the problem.

Transition sequence notation for snakes is a frequently-used alternative to vertex sequence notation. In a transition sequence, each edge of a snake is labeled with the position of the bit that varies between the labels for the two vertices incident to that edge, i.e. the base 2 logarithm of the bitwise exclusive OR of the vertices' binary labels. Transition sequence notation for the snake in Figure 1 is thus 0,1,2,0. Transition sequences presented hereinafter omit commas and follow the canonical form described by Kochut [5].

2 Priming

Priming a search with a maximal or near-maximal snake from a lower dimension simplifies search for snakes. Rather than directly searching for an n -dimensional snake, the problem becomes one of extending a known lower-dimensional snake.

To extend a known snake of dimension $n-1$, it suffices to find a compatible snake of dimension $n-1$ which can be concatenated to the known snake with a connecting edge in the n -th dimension. Two snakes are compatible if they have exactly one vertex in common which is an endpoint of both snakes.

The example below shows 2-dimensional snakes with vertex sequences 00,01,11 and 11,10. Their only common vertex, 11, is an endpoint vertex of both snakes. Concatenating the vertex sequences while prefixing the first snake's coordinates with 0 and the second snake's with 1 gives 000,001,011,111,110: the vertex sequence of a 3-dimensional snake as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. 2-dimensional snakes concatenated in 3 dimensions.

The transition sequence of the resulting 3-dimensional snake is 0120: the concatenation of the component snakes' transition sequences 01 and 0 with an intermediate edge denoted by 2.

Priming a search with a lower-dimensional seed snake extends the usefulness of search algorithms by reducing the size of the space to be searched. But the advantages of priming come at a price. Priming cannot construct the maximum-length snake in some dimensions. The first such example is in six dimensions, where all snakes of maximal length (26 edges) have canonical transition sequence 01231043054013402410431534. No digit in that sequence appears fewer than two times, thus it cannot be a concatenation of two 5-dimensional snakes.

3 $n-1$ priming

We first discuss the form of primed search that constructs an n -dimensional snake by concatenating two $n-1$ dimensional snakes as described above. We will call this $n-1$ priming to distinguish it from a technique to be discussed later that uses $n-2$ dimensional seed snakes.

In practice, $n-1$ priming gives best results when the seed snake is slightly shorter than the maximal-length snake in its dimension. Of the maximal-length (50 edge) snakes in 7-d, the ones that can be discovered by an $n-1$ primed search have 6-d subpaths of length 24 and 25, slightly shorter than the 26-edge maximum [3]. The longest (length 190) 9-d snakes the author has encountered have 8-d subpaths of 96 edges or fewer, short of the maximum of 98 in that dimension.

Extending a given $n-1$ dimensional seed snake is a search for a compatible snake in an adjacent, restricted $n-1$ dimensional space: restricted in that all but one endpoint of the seed snake's vertices are off-limits. The restricted space to be searched is thus the complement of the set of vertices in the seed snake (except for one endpoint).

The results of any primed search depend on the particular seed snake(s) chosen. Some seed snakes extend better than others.

4 $n-2$ priming

$n-2$ priming partitions an n -dimensional hypercube into $(n-2)$ -dimensional quadrants. Binary vertex coordinates in quadrant 00 start with 00, coordinates in quadrant 01 start with 01, and so on.

$n-2$ priming requires two $(n-2)$ -dimensional seed snakes that are nearly identical, differing only near one endpoint. One seed snake will be placed in quadrant 01 and the other in quadrant 10, i.e. one seed snake's vertex coordinates will be prefixed with binary digits 01 and the other with 10. We present an example using two 11-dimensional seed snakes whose transition sequences 23751...12432 and 23751...12430 differ only in their last digits. (Complete transition sequences are in the Appendix.) We show a method to concatenate those two seed snakes with two compatible extension snakes to form a 13-dimensional snake.

The union of the vertex sets of the two nearly-identical seed snakes is a path with a branch at one end; this is symbolized in Figure 3 by a snake with a forked

tongue. The shaded areas in quadrants 01 and 10 represent the seed snakes in those quadrants. The shaded area in quadrant 11 represents the complement of the union of the two seed snakes' vertex sets.

Fig. 3. $n-2$ priming with seed snakes in quadrants 01 and 10.

The right tip of the snake's tongue in quadrant 10 represents an endpoint vertex of that quadrant's seed snake. It connects via a dashed arc (representing an inter-quadrant edge in the n -dimensional hypercube) to a corresponding vertex in quadrant 11, to be used as the initial vertex in search for a compatible snake in that quadrant. That search is symbolized by a squiggly arrow continuing off into the shaded area in quadrant 11.

Similarly, the left tip of the seed snake's tongue in quadrant 01 represents an endpoint vertex of that snake and connects to a corresponding vertex in quadrant 00, the initial vertex in a search for a snake whose vertices lie in the shaded area in that quadrant.

The tails of the two seed snakes are connected by two inter-quadrant edges in series, shown by dashed arcs. As the seed snakes are not in adjacent quadrants, they connect via an intermediate vertex in quadrant 00. A circular area surrounding that vertex in the diagram is not shaded, illustrating that vertices adjacent to it must be considered off-limits while searching in quadrant 00.

Whereas $n-1$ priming searches for a single compatible $(n-1)$ -dimensional snake, $n-2$ priming searches for two $(n-2)$ -dimensional snakes. In the example presented here, the resulting composite 12-d snake has endpoints in quadrants 00 and 11.

In the 13-d example given in the Appendix, 11-d seed snakes in quadrants 01 and 10 each have 736 edges. The extension snake in quadrant 11 found by beam search has 719 edges. (Beam search is heuristically pruned breadth-first search as described in [1].) The extension snake found in quadrant 00 is shorter at 697 edges. Available space in quadrant 00 is reduced by the intrusion of an intermediate connecting vertex. The composite 13-d snake, including its 4 inter-quadrant edges, has $697+736+736+719+4=2892$ edges.

Although the results presented here used beam search to find compatible snakes, $n-1$ and $n-2$ priming can both be used with a wide range of search algorithms.

In the 13-d example with $n-2$ priming given in the Appendix, the paired seed snakes are equal in length—but that is not a requirement. The branches of the forked tongue in Figure 3 may be unequal in length. The 12-d snake detailed in the Appendix was found using 10-d seed snakes of lengths 376 and 373.

5 $n-1$ and $n-2$ priming compared

Compared to $n-1$ priming, $n-2$ priming reduces by one the dimension of the required seed snake(s). It also reduces the dimension of the space to be searched at each step. This is beneficial, as Snake-in-the-Box algorithms typically perform better when searching in smaller dimensional spaces.

$n-2$ priming aims to make efficient use of space in hypercube graphs. As the two seed snakes it uses are nearly identical, their union restricts the remaining two quadrants less than the union of two dissimilar snakes would. This advantage is however offset by the need to sacrifice vertices adjacent to an intermediate vertex required to connect the two seed snakes. With increasing dimension, the balance of these two effects shifts in favor of $n-2$ priming.

$n-2$ priming outperformed $n-1$ priming in beam search with dimensions $n=12$ and $n=13$; in lower dimensions, $n-1$ priming gave better results.

$n-2$ priming requires a pair of seed snakes, identical except for divergence near one endpoint. Such pairs are harder to find than the individual seed snakes used in $n-1$ priming.

6 Results

Table 1 compares primed beam search results with those from Meta-NRPA (Nested Rollout Policy Adaptation, a form of Monte Carlo search) [2] which gave the best previous records known to the author in dimensions 10-12. Beam search used $n-1$ priming in dimensions 10 and 11 (see [1] for transition sequences) and $n-2$ priming in dimensions 12 and 13 (see Appendix).

Beam search code for this work was written in C++, compiled by gcc, and run under Ubuntu Linux on an Intel i5-12600K processor. Each run used less than 30 GiB of RAM.

dimension	beam search	Meta-NRPA
10	376	373
11	736	721
12	1461	1383
13	2892	2709

Table 1. Comparison of $n-1$ and $n-2$ primed beam search and Meta- Nested Rollout Policy Adaptation. [2]

7 Summary

$n-1$ and $n-2$ priming enabled a beam search algorithm with simple heuristics to outperform previously published results for Snake-in-the-Box in dimensions 10 and above. $n-2$ priming was the superior priming method in dimensions 12 and 13, and $n-1$ priming in lower dimensions.

8 Acknowledgement

Thanks to Randall Munroe, whose comic xkcd #3125 [6] introduced the author to the Snake-in-the-Box problem.

References

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2. C. Dang, C. Bazgan, T. Cazenave, M. Morgan, P-H. Wuillemin (2023), Warm-Starting Nested Rollout Policy Adaptation with Optimal Stopping, *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* 37 (10): 12381–12389.
3. T. E. Drapela, The Snake-in-the-Box Problem: a primer, MSc Thesis, Athens, Georgia (2015).
4. W. H. Kautz, Unit-distance error-checking codes, *IRE Trans. Electronic Computers* EC-7 (1958) 179–180.
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A Appendix

The hexadecimal transition sequence for a length-1461 12-dimensional snake found by beam search with $n-2$ priming appears below with edges grouped by quadrants. The two central quadrants are the seed snakes of length 376 and 373. The **a** and **b** transitions are inter-quadrant edges.

Transition sequences for record-length snakes in dimensions 1-13 can be found on a web page maintained by the author at <https://minortriad.com/snake/>

```
0123451602 1046102542 0640125712 0461560120 4620124537
1206401671 2046021042 7457042104 6017612408 5402167106
4021406356 0421046024 5064021046 3710254174 2102460210
6736012064 2015610460 2160459021 0460120516 0210461021
7237510217 4604210460 2450460210 6316402542 1046824604
2104602450 4602163106 4021406716 0210461025 4174210246
0210427021 0461360120 4620156104 6021604783 7406120640
25421049
```

a

```
                                406410 2460452046 0216046754
6042104602 4521361254 2162560452 6724604210 4602450640
2160736012 0639602163 1064021406 7160210461 0254174210
2460210427 0210461360 1204620156 1046021604 6754604210
4602452098 0254206401 2406457640 6120640165 1026402106
3164012072 4012064201 2471452016 4012061760 4120460136
1204924602 1071602104 6102167265 1024602104 2740612064
0234210460 5610460216 0461541760 4210460245 2014601206
```

ba

```
6021064102 5420640124 0671451640 6120640165 0640124320
4602160472 4012064201 5627612016 4012061701 2064294021
6310640214 0671602104 6102541742 1024602104 2702104613
6012046201 5610460216 0467546042 1046024520 8902542064
0124064576 4061206401 6510264021 0631640120 7240120642
0124714520 1640120617 6041204601 3612069360 2106370612
0460542064 0124064276 2540652612 4521631254 2064012406
4576406120 6402540642 012
```

a

```
1520164012 0617012064 0254064201 4604271246 1360120642
0156104602 1604672640 1204524602 4165921046 0210716021
0461021546 0472406410 2460473421 0460561046 0216046154
1760421046 0245201460 1204894021 0641025420 6401240671
4516406120 6401650640 1243204602 1604754671 6021046102
1725046012 0645971640 6120640165 1274206401 2406726012
0370210642 7602106402 1754716421 6046736406 1249204602
```

The hexadecimal transition sequence for a length-2892 13-dimensional snake found by beam search with $n-2$ priming appears below with edges grouped by quadrants. The two central quadrants are the seed snakes, each of length 736. The **b** and **c** transitions are inter-quadrant edges.

```
01203420123053240124320462342012451201750124320175012073201234120630243
21032451420123412842341742102360342103765304102430140621023420540132410
91421023421362432102415423012342036021432102370210324514201234120640234
21053012034201230549534230123420362342012342a16203420123053475423102342
05423401764321024326153673123420132437143021571023421671243217812341742
10243021641234201423504603423146234201471243201324514201234120163423503
21024302189120342012305324361021432102415423102342174102432641324306405
32410243214612034201247143208301234264123420142341631520124306320123412
017a1234201471243201324514201234120165012034201230510341742102430216412
342014235046034231203420a602105142012341206130124301503213
```

```
b
23421641024301651031542347012034201245143013241360214321024152102432102
75324102432068023420142350321024302164054102143210241521024307320123405
43241024321462432102415423102342196124320132451420123412016342351401703
42301234203623420123053241024321461203420124714320830123426412342014234
16315423012342036021432102370342012514201234120145046120342012305324012
43219a12342014235032102430216405410214321024152102430732012341206302432
10324513614324102432146243210380234174210243021641234201423504603423012
34203623420147124320132451420123412016342350321024302198120342012305324
31602143210241542310234217410243263024321032430640532410243214612034201
24714321871234217612430632450243201324350764321024164350321024302650615
36731234201324371430215732
```

```
bc
23751203417342310243213763
51605620342012305346142012346705342310234205423603421671243217812341742
10243021641234201423504603423012342036234201471243201324514201234120613
42350321024302189120342012305324361021432102415423102342174102432630243
21032430640532410243214612034201247143208301234264123420142341631542301
23420360214321023703420125142012341201450461203420123053241024321a91234
21042350321024302164054102143210241521024307320123412063024321032451361
43241024321462432103802341742102430216412342014235032102432630243210324
30710415324361021432102415423102342169124320132451420123426412342014234
50432102370342012514201234120145046120342012305324102432086023420142357
20123420125142012341206314231034154210243021074324513015610342014612430
```

```
b
50342103160214321024152102432105734102430532012341206302432103245130143
21038023417421024302164123420142350460342301234203623420147124320132451
42012341201634235032102430219812034201230532436102143210241542310234217
41024326302432103243064053241024321461203420124714321871234217612432017
50416203420123053475423102342054234017643210243261536201430732012340a34
23102342174102432630243210324306405324102432146120432012475421023153243
61021432102469420143641234201423465342301234203602143210237034201251420
12341201450461203420123053241024320830124714321025032102430210351360214
32102415423012342176124321032435102164123420142350410342390234201630120
34201230520123420360214321024167542301234203602134210231532410243214624
321038023
```